

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF IMPLICATIONS OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY ON WEAKER SECTIONS OF SOCIETY IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Education is the basic need of every citizen in the country that helps to change the society by improving and strengthening skills, ethical values, scientific temper, social equality, fraternity, Justice and feelings of nationality. In this paper an attempt has been made to discuss the provisions made in the NEP-2020 to cater the problems of downtrodden and marginalized people of India. The comparative study of educational status of India and other countries reveals the need to seriously focus on the different aspects to improve the provisions made in education system. It is also necessary to make provisions in NEP to safeguard the constitutional rights of SC/ST/OBC/MC people and ensure them freedom for their future progress.

Keywords: NEP, Human Development Index, Total Fertility Rate, GER

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Introduction:

The world is undergoing rapid changes in the knowledge landscape with various scientific and Technological advances by educational progress. Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential to acquire knowledge for economic growth, social justice, equality and to promote humanism. In NEP; it agrees that India is still at a distance from developing an equitable and just society. Education is the process by which country can achieve overall progress. India is a diversified country with a variety of cultures, religions, castes and social groups [1]. Unless these underprivileged sections of society receive the minimum education, they can not exercise the civil, political, economic and social freedom enshrined in the constitution of India. Equality, in education, would be a cornerstone of high vision for prosperous, harmonious, equitable and ever evolving society [2].

Indian must be proud for their rich tradition of imparting knowledge by developing world's first and oldest Buddhist University system as Nalanda, Taxshila and Vikramshila. Students from across the world were attracted to Indian knowledge system. Education was considered at higher virtue in ancient India [3]. However in the medieval period of Indian history, the big strata of outcaste people were deprived off from education due to few high class people considered education was their monopoly. It was not only the custom to deny the education to lower caste (SC/ST/OBC) people but it was written code of conduct enshrined in the religious book of *Manusmriti*. It was in the eighteenth century, the British people who started some colleges and schools for all in the Indian provinces.

The British government had introduced modern education in India from Macaulay's minute to Wood's dispatch to several commissions like Sadler Commission; Indian Education Policy(1904) etc. build the foundation of the Indian

Education system during the colonial period. After independence, Radhakrishnan Committee constituted in 1948-49 was focused on higher education. The Kothari Commission(1964-66) had a holistic approach and advised the government on the national pattern of education. Based on the recommendations of the Kothari Commission, the government announced national policy on education 1968, which focused on equal educational opportunities in order to achieve national integration. The Kothari Commission had proposed to establish Indian Education Services and common school system. The National Policy on Education 1986 whose objective was to emphasis on the removal of disparities and to equalize educational opportunities [4]. To cater the challenges in education system the government has started to implement New Education Policy 2020[1]. This paper will try to analyze the facts and figures education status and the provisions made with respect to previous policies and current requirement of general to marginalized peoples of India. This paper is critically analyzing the only those issues in the NEP 2020 which are concerned with its effect on marginalized peoples.

Methodology:

In this paper, the research is based on the secondary data. The data has taken from the different reports, journal and research papers, union budget, AISHE reports. It has mainly focus on comparative study of relative values of various education policies. The higher education status in research publications of India is compared with United States and China. The measures reported in the draft of NEP -2020 has analyzed by case wise to show its impact on future of downtrodden people. It is also focused to examine data of SC/ST/OBC with respect to GER and provisions to cater challenges.

Results and Discussion:

In India, modern education is a significant tool to bring about justice, liberty, equality fraternity among the citizen of multilingual, multi-religious and multiethnic country. Education in this respect is conceived as an instrument of social and economic change for the future democratic society [5]. I would like to propose the pragmatic approach when any new policy is to be designed. It means, if any old process/ policy can not to be applied as it is but can be used by after some modification then do that. If some process or values are very necessary and useful to present generation then keep using these provisions for betterment of future generation. If it is outdated and can not be continued then discard it. Is this pragmatic approach considered by the draft committee when framing this New Education Policy? Generally, Ideology of the ruling government reflects in the policy and programmes. In concerned with this approach, let us decode the intent and content of the New Education Policy 2020 of India.

Facts of Educational status in India accepted in NEP 2020 and by other agencies.

1. A large proportion of students currently in elementary school - estimated to be over 5 crore in number - have not attained foundational literacy and numeracy (2.1 of NEP).
2. Currently, with the lack of universal access to ECCE, a large proportion of children already fall behind within the first few weeks of Grade 1. (2.5 NEP).
3. The GER for Grades 6-8 was 90.9%, while for Grades 9-10 and 11-12 it was only 79.3% and 56.5%, As per the 75th round household survey by NSSO in 2017-18, the number of out of school children in the age group of 6 to 17 years is 3.22 crore.
4. There are 1,08,017 single-teacher schools and majority of them (85743) being primary schools.
5. India spend on research only 0.69% of GDP as compared to 2.8% in the United States of America, 4.3% in Israel

and 4.2% in South Korea (17.3 NEP).

6. The current public (Government - Centre and States) expenditure on education in India has been around 4.1% of GDP (Analysis of Budgeted Expenditure 2017-18).

Merit and Research achievements:

The NEP has mentioned the word 'merit' many times in the draft, so it is necessary to evaluate the merit of those who have captured the key positions in higher education institutions and research laboratories (90% of total posts) from many years. However, the proportions of SC/ST/OBC in the faculty position and research scholars have been very less as compared to the general candidates from the independence. If so, Why India did not get a noble prize and not listed a single institute in the rank of top 200 Universities of the world? If we compare the data in Fig 1, there is no any substantial increase in the number of researchers in India from 1996 to 2016. The hugenumber of researchers in US clearly shows the advancement in research and technology.

Fig. 1 Comparative chart of number of researchers per one million inhabitants of US, China and India

The business enterprises in US have spent fifteen times more than India and amount spend on higher education is thirty times more than India. All business enterprises, banking sector, bureaucrats, secretary, Vice-chancellors, policy makers and Ministers were belongs to higher caste in India. Fig. 2 shows the Comparative values of number of patent applications filed during 2009 to 2017 of US, China and India. In 2017, US have filed 293904 patents, China 1245709 patents and India 1496[6]. This huge gap clearly reflects the status of merit of high caste faculty and students. Then, how the reservation in education was deteriorated the education system?

Fig. 2 Comparative chart of number of patent applications filed during 2009 to 2017 of US, China and India.

(Data: world intellectual property right organization)

The representation of students belonging to Scheduled Caste (SC), Scheduled Tribe (ST) and Other Backwards Classes (OBC) categories in the PhD programmes of premier science institutions remains poor, according to data released by the Ministry of Education (MoE) in Rajya Sabha. Of the 25007 Ph.D scholars admitted in the 23 IITs over the five year period, only 9% of SC and 2.1% of ST represented. The situation of SC/ST students were come into focus when Rohit Vemula had committed suicide due to caste discrimination. Therefore, reservation is not responsible for the poor performance in research and development as compared to developed country. Education Quality Upgradation and Inclusion Program (EQUIP) report mentioned the fact of lack of scientific approach as ‘the culture of questioning and reasoning has not inculcated as a part of higher education in most of institutions.

Fig 3 Number of research publications of US, China and India during 1996 to 2016.

The research publication scenario in India is shown in the Fig. 3, which explains the comparative position against the US and China[6]. As per the Fig 3, Number of research publications of US, China and India during 1996 to 2016 indicates poor performance of the high caste people of India in the research publication. The spending of US on R&D as proportion of GDP is 2.74% and that of India 0.62%, the GDP of US is 21.3 lakh Cr \$ and India 2.8 Lakh Cr \$[12]. The mentality of high caste officials in the higher education institution is reflected in the statement of Prof. Malik B.N. of JNU Delhi in the Academic council reported in Outlook magazine dated 26th April 2010 ‘some castes are genetically malnourished and so very little can be achieved in raising them up and if they are, it would be undergoing excellence and merit’

Higher Education Scenario of India:

India’s higher education was started by British with the establishment of University in 1857. After Independence, in India there were 27 Universities, 578 colleges, two lakh students in 36 cr population. At present there are 993 Universities, 40,000 colleges, 3.8 cr students are enrolled in India. State government funding on higher education is 60 to 65% of total government funding[18]. Share of central government was 30% of total expenditure on education even though NEP had made many provisions to keep overall education sector under centrals control although education is in concurrent list. This NEP has drafted by a person from America and accepted K-12 model of non affiliation and scraped British model of affiliation which was continued from 150 years.

Table 1.Last Eight decades Higher education data of India.

Sr. No	Year	No. of Universities	No. of Colleges	Enrollment in Million	GER	Population Cr	Expenditure on education % GDP
01	1951	27	578	0.2	0.8	36	0.6
02	1961	49	1819	0.6	1.5	44	1.5
03	1971	102	3277	2.0	4.2	55	2.11
04	1981	132	4577	2.8	4.7	68	2.9
05	1991	185	6627	4.4	5.9	84	3.8
06	2001	260	11146	8.8	8.1	102	3.34
07	2011	621	34908	28.5	19.4	120	3.8
08	2019	893	39931	37.5	26.3	135	3.2

Data Source Vargeses and AISHE various years.

Poverty in India is alarming among the downtrodden people of the society. Education is expected to play a vital role to eradicate the poverty but the percentage of people acquiring the higher education in SC/ST/OBC is very low. If you compare the economic situation of Indian people with other countries of the world then it was found that per capita income of US is 50 times more than India, human development index of India ranks 134th and Global Hunger Index of India ranks 96th among 119 developing countries.

GER of Scheduled Caste is ½ of General and ST 1/3 of general category students. Now the question is how much time SC/ST will take to achieve the GER of general caste people? What has received back to these marginalized tax payers of citizen of India from last eight decades as their number in education sector is marginal? That means whatever government has spent on education that was utilized for the betterment of affluent section of society.

Who needs higher education? Why? Higher education equips SC/ST/OBC person with proper lexicon to articulate their issues, their political aspirations, their voices against atrocities and fulfillment of their social duties and responsibilities. Already suffered higher education of marginalized people has come into danger by multiple exit schemes. Many factors like poverty, humiliation, caste discrimination and the hectic atmosphere will force the students of marginalized society to exit from education. This leads to increase the drop out rate rather to decrease it. The financing of research through NRF also seems troubling as it seems that the government wants to divert more funds to ancient knowledge systems rather than creating new knowledge and technologies.

The subtlety of NEP is to lure backward class into the abyss of vocational courses and to destroy their path to articulation. The idea behind to shift year of graduation from three to four year is to make an arrangement to higher caste students to get an easy admission in American Universities as it is mandatory condition. Research topic will be decided by National Research Association that has taken away your freedom to choose research topics. If the committee members of NRA are of brahmanical ideology, then they will not permit to carry on research on genuine problems. The Higher Education Institutions or Universities will be a Board of Governance (BoG) and filled undemocratically by selection. This will lead to control of power by the peoples of brahmanical ideology and that kind of thinking.

Education and Population:

Education is a vital aspect of population change, social development and economic growth of every society and also helps to control population growth. Population explosion is become a major problem of the world. The person with

the vision Dr. B. R. Ambedkar in 1938 had placed the bill about family planning in the Bombay assembly for the solution of poorness and to improve social and economic condition of India but the congress rejected that bill. In the year 1951, the population of India was 34 Cr and today it is reached to 135 cr. The country of 2.4% earth surface is holding 17% of total population of world with population density 400/Sqr Km.

Fig. 4a & b Effect of education on total fertility rate (TFR).

(Population, education and development report by UNO 2003)

Why India is facing this alarming situation? The fundamental reason is that government has not implemented proper education policy. From last many years, education was the monopoly of few high caste people and they have not changed their mentality still and restricted the process of universalization of education. Fig.4 shows the effect of education on the total fertility rate. A woman with higher level of education desires small family. The graph explains the number of children per women is decreased by increasing the education level and rate of fertility also decreased with the growth of education.

Constitutional provisions for SC/ST/OBC and NEP-2020.

Article 46 of the Constitution, in the Directive Principles of State Policy, says: "The state shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and, in particular, of the Scheduled Castes (SCs) and the Scheduled Tribes (STs) and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation". Article 45 in the Constitution of India explains 'The state shall endeavor to provide, within a period of ten years from commencement of this Constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years'. The NEP 2020 has not mentioned anywhere this constitutional clause. The SC/ST/OBC, the constitutional words are replaced by Socio-economically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs). This change will deprive the constitutional rights of SC/ST/OBC and hamper their overall development. The principle of equality if not adopted in education then how it will percolate in the society. The reservation in employment and admission to SC/ST/OBC has enshrined in the constitution of India in article 15, 16 of fundamental right. If it is expected that the government of India should protect the fundamental rights of all citizens then how it is denied in NEP by not mentioning any such a provision. NEP-1986 has clearly mentioned the objective as 'a special emphasis on the removal of disparities and to equalize educational opportunities' and provision of reservation in part III for women and part IV for SC/ST/OBC. One needs to compare the provision between NEP 1986 and 2020 with respect to marginalized class. In 1986 education policy the following measures for SC/ST have mentioned;

- Incentives to indigent families to send their children to school.

- Ensure timely and prompt payment of pre-matric and post-metric scholarship.
- Incentives for uniform, books, stationary etc.
- Micro planning and verification should be done to ensure the enrollment, retention, and successful completion of course of SC/ST students.
- The well administrative setup and committees to monitor and review implementation of all educational programs for SC/ST/OBC.

Nothing is so unequal as equal treatment for unequal. The NEP 2020 is completely silent over reservation of SC/ST/OBC/women. The reservation word has not mentioned even once in NEP however the draft consistently emphasizes 'merit-based criteria for admission at all levels, for selection, appointment of faculty and promotion during their carrier. How such a 'meritorious knowledge society' can be imagined without addressing the issues of centuries of exclusion and oppression of lower caste and gender discrimination? Dr. B. R. Ambedkar explained the solution on this in Bombay Legislative council 'If all these communities are to be brought to the level of equality, then the only remedies is to adopt the principle of inequality and to give favored treatment to those who are at below level.

Table 2 Year wise amount of unutilized and not allotted funds to SC/ST from last 20 years.

Sr. No	Year	Central Govt Budget	Plan Expenditure	22.5 % to be allotted to SC/ST	Actual allotment to SC/ST	Difference	Unspent amount	Total amount not allotted + unutilized
1	2000-2001	325611	82669	18600.53	5700	12900	1710	14610
2	2001-2002	375223	95100	21397.5	6000	15397	1800	17197
3	2002-2003	410309	113500	25537.5	7500	18037	2250	20287
4	2003-2004	438795	120974	27219.15	8000	19219	2400	21619
5	2004-2005	497682	132276	29762.1	11000	18762	3300	22062
6	2005-2006	514341	143497	32286.83	12000	20286	3600	23886
7	2006-2007	563991	172728	38863.8	14096	24767	4228.8	28996
8	2007-2008	680521	205100	46147.5	19876	26271	5962.8	32234
9	2008-2009	883956	275235	61927.88	23953	37974	7185.9	45160
10	2009-2010	1020883	325149	73158.53	25140	48018	7542	55560
11	2010-2011	1108749	373092	83945.7	32772	51173	9831.6	61005
12	2011-2012	1304365	412375	92784.38	48987	43797	14696.1	58493
13	2012-2013	1490925	521025	117230.6	58823	58407	17646.9	76054
14	2013-2014	1665297	555322	124947.5	66159	58788	19847.7	78636
15	2014-2015	1663673	422644	95094.9	82935	12159	24880.5	37040
16	2015-2016	1777477	465277	104687.3	50851	53836	15255.3	69091
17	2016-2017	1978060	550010	123752.3	62838	60914	18851.4	79765
18	2017-2018	2146735	644020	144904.5	84313	60591	25293.9	85885
19	2018-2019	2442213	732663	164849.2	95754	69095	28726.2	97821
20	2019-2020	2786349	835904	188078.4	126887	61191	38066.1	99257
							Total	1023667

(Data collected from union budget for planed expenditure and for SCP Jadhav Committee reports. For 2001 to 2005 data of amount allocation produced by taking an average proportionate of other years figures)

The planning commission in its 10th Five year plan mid term review reports said that only about 50% of allocated funds were being utilized for SC/ST. Ministries is reluctant to use funds for SC/ST development. The table 2 gives detailed information regarding the amount of funds not utilized and funds not allotted in the year wise central budget. This data helps us to understand the total governing system and their mentality about the implementation of policy. The huge amount 10.23 lakh Cr have not utilized from last twenty years for the upliftment of poor downtrodden people of this country. On an average, fifty thousand crore rupees per year were unutilized by central government. As an equal amount of funds have not allocated or utilized by the state governments. This is mercy killing of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe people in this democratic nation. UNICEF in the report 'state of world's children' mentioned the 8.8 lakh children below 5 years died in 2018 due to malnutrition and India stands 102 position in Global Hunger Index. Who are these children? Are they from affluent sections of society? They are belongs to most deprived SC/ST castes. Can any one say this democracy is for the people of the country and freedom of the people of the country? This is still a pertinent question asked by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar after the seventy years of independence.

NEP and Privatization.

The policy of (NPE) 1986 had already made way for the entry of private interests which further got explored after the neo-liberal reforms of 1991. A decade back, the present policy was preceded by the Policy Framework for Reforms in Education (PFRE), convened by Mukesh Ambani, with Kumar Mangalam Birla as its member. It advocated foreign direct investment in higher education and also initiated the idea of private universities bill. In 2001, the numbers of private institutions were 3000 and government 9800. Now, the numbers of private institutions are 23000 and government 13000. The pleasant-sounding phrases like public-spirited private', 'philanthropic private' and 'Public Philanthropic Partnership' are used to mislead the people. About 45.2% of college enrolment in India is now in private unaided colleges, and another 21.2% is in private aided institutions. In Maharashtra, there are only 12 government engineering colleges and 300 private engineering colleges explains the real facts of education system. Total 8.8% SC, 2.4% ST and 5% Muslim students are enrolled for undergraduate courses however all these three contribute 40% of population. For undergraduate professional courses 15 lakhs are enrolled in government institutes and 60.5 lakhs in private colleges.

NEP is nothing but the bigger gate for the privatization of education sector. It repeatedly emphasizes that both the public and private components of the system must be treated equally. Autonomy is another name of privatization and the end of reservation. The abolition of UGC implies that government wants to hand over the education to private players and to keep in hand process of allocation of fund instead of setting independent funding agency like UGC. If the privatization process enhanced then access, equity and inclusiveness will be denied. Due to privatization, education becomes commodities instead of way of living life.

The constitution of India provides us fundamental right in article 21 to live with dignity; however as per NEP, there won't be a permanent appointment and only five-year probation and tenure track. There is a golden hand shake called compensation, which will throw out the people from their job. In 2001 the government institutes were the double of private institutes and now the case is reversed. Is it not the privatization of education? Now the fundamental question is what will be consequences of privatization on the future of SC/ST/OBC.

Other issues of NEP

a) It has proposed in NEP to achieve GER 50% in 2035. How is it possible by reducing 993 Universities and 40000

- b) colleges into 15000 multidisciplinary institutes? Another thing is, the GER per district is different as per its demographic conditions. If GER for these backward districts is around 7 then by what ways it will be raised to 50%.
- c) For the better quality education, Student teacher ratio proposed to be kept below 30:1, however other countries has PTR very low as Canada: 9:1, Sweden 12:1, Russia 10:1 and US 12:1 then how the quality of education will be maintained.
- d) In the draft, the names of many high caste historical intellectuals have mentioned and discriminately forget the names of Buddhists intellects who were flourished many ancients Universities, through their knowledge impressed the whole world.
- e) In NEP section II (9.1), it has mentioned to improvise democratic values however the NEP 2020 was passed without discussion in the parliament and not considered suggestions out of lakhs of ideas sent by citizens.
- f) In 2011 census shows the number of English speaker are very small because when people record English as second language, it is not counted. However, Sanskrit speakers are more because even it mentioned as second language, it is counted. This will go towards the creating Sanskrit-based past culture; though Sanskrit is no longer a living language. This will keep away the students from marginalized section to learn world's popular language English and subsequent opportunities to expand the horizons.
- g) Two opposite views and objectives are proposed in policy, one is to inculcate scientific temper, critical thinking, reasoning ability and another one is to follow the ancient customs and culture. If there is conflict between ethics and vested interested it is observed the intellectual prefer to vested interest. Deep rooted customs in Indian people restricted the innovative, cognitive and scientific thinking process. Some of this is simply customary lip-service to these ideals, and the hypocrisy in it can be gauged from the actual record of respect that the Government has displayed for these ideals.
- h) The education policy of that country will get succeed whose industrial policy is succeeded. China has implemented first industrial policy and then education policy. India's today's major problem is unemployment. There were no any steps taken towards to frame out effective industrial policy of India.
- i) The common school system, suggested by Kothari commission, is completely scraped by this policy. In the section 3.3 of NEP, it is mentioned to provide equitable and quality education to all children up to the age of 18. How is it possible and achieved without common school system? Ambernath Rai "The only way to remove the discrimination in the school system is to introduce common school system in the country which will ensure uniform quality of education to all the children in the country".
- j) The per capita income and GER are very less in disadvantaged section of society. If government has the honest intention to increase the GER to 50 till 2035 then it is required to increase per capita annual income of the poor people up to two lakh per person.
- k) As per the Sengupta Committee Report, 77% of people are able spend 20 rupees per day then how the online education will ensure the equitable and quality education to all children.
- l) During last seventy years, does any government had focused on to eradicate caste system, corruption, gender disparity, poverty during the framing the education policy. Thousand of teachers and lakhs of students are studying science from last seventy years, even though why superstitions prevail in society? Thousand of teachers and lakhs of students are studying commerce, economics, finance, and management from last seventy years, even though why

poverty prevails in the society? Thousand of teachers and lakhs of students are studying social science from last seventy years, even though why caste system, atrocities on women and wrong customs prevail in society? Thousand of teachers and lakhs of students are studying politics from last seventy years, even though why people unable select their representative and understand the democratic values?

Suggestions to review NEP: The Government must consider the following points.

- a) Instead of formation of autonomous institutes we should continue the Process of affiliation of institutes to the Universities.
- b) Government should start nationalization of education and stop complete private institutes as per banking sector reforms in 1968.
- c) There should not be discrimination in the status of school and education. Government must start 'Common School System' immediately.
- d) As per the Knowledge Commission Report, Establish two Universities (General and Professional) in every district of India. If required it can be increased.
- e) Why not for good and noble cause of education for all government keep donation to education box in every school, temples.
- f) The Chairman of Kothari commission emphasized on freedom of Education from political influence that must be maintained.
- g) Government should focus to eradicate poverty especially SC/ST and allocate govt. land for cultivation as it was observed that economic well being improve the enrollment.
- h) It is need of an hour that government should allocate and utilize Planned expenditure on SC/ST/OBC as per their population and set mechanism to allot Non-Plan expenditure to SC/ST/OBC as per their proportionate of population.
- i) Start Indian Education Services and select reserved candidates through separate selection committee comprise SC/ST/OBC members only for interview.
- j) It is new paradigm shift in education to Start salary to the SC/ST/OBC students.
- k) To achieve 50% GER till 2035 allocate fund of 8% of GDP on education.
- l) Every village must have at least one primary school with all facilities.
- m) Teacher should not be assigned non-academic work.
- n) Government should appoint bawarchi and Separate mechanism for Mid-day meal.
- o) Each village must have Library.
- p) At every stage of governing body, there must have proper representation of SC/ST/OBC/CM/women.
- q) Social Practical should be a part of curricula to make awareness among the villagers as Science students: superstition, water harvesting, environment; Political Science: Importance of democracy and constitutional rights; Sociology: caste annihilation, women's right; Agriculture: New agricultural processes, market structure.

The NEP 2020 is found to be more inclined towards the privatization of education system in India and fostering the economic and educational gap between the have and have not people. It is necessary to consider, during the preparation of draft of NEP, the local conditions, facts and objectives set in the preamble of the constitution to achieve above suggestions.

Conclusion:

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential to acquire knowledge for overall development. Education of marginalized people in India is suffering with lack of school facilities, inspiration, proper conditions, high drop out ratio, low GER etc. The high population rate in India due to poor education facilities, high illiteracy and low rate of higher education of women. India is lagging behind in patent registration, number of researcher per million population and number of research paper publication if compared with US and China. NEP targeted to achieve GER 50% but it will be difficult by reducing 40000 colleges to 15000 HEI. The funds allocated to the development of SC/ST through plan expenditure from union budget is less than proportionate of population and 50% non utilization of allotted fund pulled the people in the grave poverty. For the development of country and the people of the country, government should stop the privatization of education sector and adopt Common School System and allocate funds of 8% of GDP on education.

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